

New vista in Parkinson's disease treatment: Magic of nanotechnology

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Parkinson's disease (PD) is one of the progressive neurological diseases that are associated with the loss of dopaminergic neurons in substantia nigra pars compacta of brain. Administration of drugs such as levodopa or dopamine agonists helps to increase dopamine concentration but is impeded by the endothelial layer of blood-brain barrier resulting ineffective treatment. Nanotechnology approaches have created new vistas in order to solve this burning issue. 85 nm PEGylated immunoliposome encapsulated tyrosine hydroxylase expression plasmid effectively crosses blood brain barrier and restores motor behaviour in rat model. Non-viral gene therapy comprising of Lactoferrin modified nanoparticle vectors of size 196 ± 10 nm have generated neuro protective effects. Additionally another agent known as poly-hydroxylated fullerene derivative $C_{60}(OH)_{24}$ induces positive effect in MPP+ induced PD model with its free radical scavenging activity and antioxidant potential. Equally revealing is the information about smart material namely cerium oxide nanoparticle or nanoceria as a ROS scavenger to decrease oxidative stress. In this review, attempt has been made to evaluate the role of nanotechnology for the remediation of PD.

Keywords: Parkinson's disease, dopamine, blood-brain-barrier, neuroprotection, nanotechnology.

Introduction

Over 10 million people worldwide suffer from many progressive neurological disorders namely Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease (PD). Between these two, one of the most prominent ones is PD¹. Till now the exact cause behind the onset of the diseases remains unexplored and a sincere medical attention is needed due to the lack of treatment efficacy. Parkinson's disease (PD) is one such disorder of the Central Nervous system (CNS) that affects the motor system mainly. Symptoms include movement problems like shaking, rigidity etc. leading to behavioural problems and dementia at later stages. Although the underlying cause for many PD patients is still unknown, studies have revealed that the main neurochemical effect of PD is the degeneration of dopamine secreting cells in substantia nigra pars compacta of brain². As a consequence, impairment of ubiquitin mediated proteosomal activity, protein aggregation and mitochondrial dysfunction takes place. The key player behind the protein aggregation linked to PD has been identified as α Synuclein³. Multiple facets of this protein activity have been elucidated in course of studies by various research groups unravelling etiology and pathogenesis of PD^{4,5}. This

has been discussed in the following sections because of its immense roles and connectivity with the disease.

Disease of shaking palsy: The current problem

The on-going treatments include administering dopamine agonists like duodopa, levodopa etc. that help alleviating the symptoms². But in most cases these drugs (taken orally) fail to reach their targets in brain due to the blood brain barrier. As a consequence they are metabolized in liver and kidney. In order to achieve better results, more and more drug is to be ingested leading to their accumulation in kidney and liver. This blood brain barrier between the brain extra-cellular fluid and the circulating blood is composed of endothelial cells with an electrical resistivity of $0.1 \Omega m$ (Fig. 1). Drugs available in markets nowadays show limited potential to overcome this hindrance⁶. In addition to that, the drugs lose their efficacy after certain period of time. At initial stages, they seem to neutralize the symptoms but with prolonged exposure the side effects are evident. Nausea, giddiness, jerky muscle movement inclusive of "on-off symptoms" all implying movement disorder start to develop. Abnormal psychological behaviour is additionally manifested by the patients.

Fig. 1. Comparative profile of classical and nanoscale drug delivery (The figure depicts that nanoscale application of drug delivery system overcomes the hindrance of blood brain barrier in the effective functioning of drugs).

Hence need for alternative treatment that would guarantee an efficient solution to the disease has developed. Application of nanotechnology can overcome this impasse and has been used effectively to fight against the disease⁷.

The active player behind the curtain: α -Synuclein (SNCA)

The mystery of association of cell death and Parkinson's disease has not yet been solved although the prime convict is thought to be a toxic protein, Alpha Synuclein (SNCA), the main constituent of lewy body³. Studies reveal that SNCA is an acidic unstructured protein whose function is not yet explored completely. It is generally localised in the neuronal and glial cells of Substantia nigra, thalamus, neocortex and hippocampus. It is marked with a tendency to bind to the mitochondrial membrane disrupting the mitochondrial architecture. Inside the cells, the native unfolded form and membrane bound alpha helical form of SNCA remain in equilibrium. Electrical activity in neurons disrupts the association of SNCA with the membrane. Besides this, it stimulates Polo like kinase 2, an active phosphorylation partner of SNCA at

SER-129^{4,5}. Moreover, presence of reactive nitrogen species like nitric oxide and protease like calpain cause modification of SNCA. All these modifications of SNCA play pivotal role to increase its tendency to form aggregates. These aggregates are further stabilised by beta sheet like interactions. They tend to form fibrils followed by their association in an annular pore like structures. All these eventually lead to formation of lewy bodies that marks the late stage of PD^{8,9}. This small cytosolic protein modulates dopamine secretion. In presence of over expressed wildtype and mutant A53T SNCA, dopamine release is diminished. Moreover, it has been shown to modulate the activity of tyrosine hydroxylase thereby affecting dopamine metabolism (Fig. 2). Research indicates that few pathological mutations and polymorphism of SNCA bear close relationship with PD^{10,11}.

Solution through nanotechnology: A comprehensive overview

"Nano" means a dimension of 10^{-9} m. Chemicals/drugs qualifying this size are potent enough to effectively cross the blood brain barrier. In turn, the drugs can be ad-

Fig. 2. Reaction scheme for the synthesis of dopamine in neurons.

ministered at target region of the brain with a positive result. Moreover some molecules at this nano-level are marked with improved biological activities to effectively treat PD. These way problems as stated earlier associated with the improper delivery of drugs at their site of application might be solved. Various approaches of nanotechnology for the treatment of PD have been illustrated below.

Nano immuno-liposomes in rescue

PD is associated with the deficit of dopaminergic neurons in substantia nigra. Tyrosine Hydroxylation (TH) is the first rate limiting step in the biosynthesis of dopamine (Fig. 3). Starting from conversion of L-phenylalanine to L-tyrosine, it leads to the production of L-DOPA that is further converted to dopamine by aromatic amino acid decarboxylase. It is subjected to feedback inhibition of catecholamine like Dopamine. A rare autosomal disorder on chromosome 11p15.5 leads to TH deficiency. It is clinically manifested as juvenile Parkinsonism. Modulation of TH-gene expression could be an underlying cause of PD. To couple gene therapy with nanotechnology, Glial fibrillary acidic protein (GFAP) gene promoter (a brain specific gene promoter) is delivered glo-

bally after intravenous administration of GFAP-TH expression plasmids encapsulated in the interior of 85-nm PEGylated immunoliposomes¹². By virtue of nano scale property, this nano immune-liposome crosses blood brain barrier and restores normal motor behaviour in a rat model. It proves that intravenous non-viral gene therapy can be effective in global delivery of exogenous genes. Moreover ectopic expression of gene is eliminated as it causes no increase in hepatic TH activity which would otherwise have occurred if viral gene therapy is used.

Non viral gene therapy using lactoferrin-modified nanoparticle

Progressive disease like PD can last for decades. So short term treatments cannot effectively handle the situation. Multiple dosing with non-viral gene therapy has been recommended to overcome the situation. In this regard, specific receptors on blood brain barrier (BBB) can be targeted for effective gene delivery. Lactoferrin (Lf) modified nanoparticles (ligands) with a size of 196 ± 10 nm have been used to bind to the Lf receptors on endothelial cells in the BBB. They have caused marked enhancement in the exogenous gene deliv-

Fig. 3. Diagram for nano-immuno-liposomes delivery during nonviral gene therapy.

ery compared to the unmodified ligands. Therapeutic proteins like glial cell-line derived neurotrophic factor (GDNF) protect the healthy neurons and repair the damaged ones. Lf-NPs loaded with human GDNF have been implicated with neuro-protective effect and mends locomotor activity (Fig. 4). It diminishes loss of dopaminergic neurons in PD rats models. Multiple injections over particular intervals have shown to exhibit better response over single dose of injection. Moreover cytotoxicity test results approve it as safe for the gene delivery in the brain¹³.

ume ratio of the nanoparticles. From past report it is evident that 5.7 μM nanoceria can replace 527 U of SOD. Effect of nanoceria on PC12 neuron-like cells (a well studied model for neural cells) has been tested. It bestows increased dopamine secretion and better antioxidant properties on PC12 cells. However this is not free from limitations. Cerium oxide nanoparticles exhibit differential prooxidant toxicity as well as variable antioxidant protective effects based on the methods of synthesis, particle size and stabilizer inspite of having the same basic core components^{14,15}.

Fig. 4. Lf-modified nanoparticle in non viral gene therapy. The above figure shows a plasmid containing Lactoferrin nanoparticles loaded with human glial derived neurotrophic factor encoding gene. The Lf-nps recognise special receptors in the brain and cross the blood brain barrier effectively; hGDNF improves neural protection.

The smart material: Nanoceria or cerium oxide nanoparticles

Oxidative stress might be the pivotal cause for the inception of several neurodegenerative pathologies like Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease. DA neurons are susceptible to oxidative stress due to their specific metabolism. Dopamine metabolites with two hydroxyl groups exert toxic effects on dopaminergic neurons through the formation of superoxide and dopamine quinones. Cerium oxide is an oxide of the rare earth metal cerium (CeO_2). Nanoceria in the form of cerium oxide nanoparticles is marked with a unique property of Superoxide dismutase (SOD) and Catalase owing to their surface oxygen vacancies aided by coexistence of Ce^{3+} and Ce^{4+} ions. They are involved in the redox reactions behaving as reactive oxygen species (ROS) scavengers including nitric oxide radicals (Fig. 5). ROS scavenging properties of nanoceria can efficiently mitigate oxidative stress in the neural cells. Cerium oxide at nanoscale offers neuro protection and better functionality due to higher surface vol-

The story is not over: Fullerenes in the treatment of PD

Impaired mitochondrial function in association with increased superoxide dismutase activity has led to the nigral cell death marking the onset and progress of PD as mentioned earlier. Neurotoxins like 1-methyl-4-phenylpyridinium (MPP^+) are widely used to mimic animal cell model of PD. They lead to the loss of DA neurons, impair TH activity giving rise to the low levels of dopamine secretion. The potential of novel free-radical scavenger, the carboxy-fullerenes (~ 1 nm) in attenuating MPP^+ mediated toxicity has been evaluated in recent experiments. This electron deficient cage shaped molecular assembly can effectively scavenge hydroxyl, superoxide and lipid radicals (Fig. 5). Dose dependent protection has been rendered by polyhydroxylated fullerene derivative $\text{C}_{60}(\text{OH})_{24}$ against MPP^+ induced acute cellular PD model. Extensive research on this nanoparticle can offer better treatment option for PD¹⁶.

Fig. 5. Nanoceria and fullerenes scavenging reactive oxygen species (ROS).

(Picture courtesy:

For Nanoceria: Reproduced from Ref. 4064340601699 with permission from the Royal Society of Chemistry.

For Polyhydroxylated Fullerene: Vukosava Milic Torres and Viktorija Dragojevic Simic (2012). Doxorubicin-Induced Oxidative Injury of Cardiomyocytes – Do We Have Right Strategies for Prevention?,

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Conclusion

With the emerging incidence of PD, awareness has been developed albeit full remedial solution is still under development. The existing treatment methods are unable to meet up the long term consequences of the disease. With the available therapies, short term symptoms can be reduced although the patient cannot get rid of the disease completely. With the magic spell of Nanotechnology, drugs at the nano-level can easily be administered to the target sites of the brain overcoming the hindrance of blood brain barrier. Success has been made further with the nanosized molecules like nanoceria, polyhydroxylated fullerenes and molecular tweezers that effectively alleviate neurotoxicity. Molecular tweezer like CLR01 has been demonstrated to ameliorate neurotoxicity targeting α Synuclein oligomers¹⁷. However challenges are evident in the form of corona formation during the treatment of nanoparticles in presence of biological macromolecules like proteins. It is having dual effects by the change

of the integrity of the nanoparticles along with the structural alteration of biological macromolecules. Corona formation is often associated with the induction of inflammatory response¹⁸. Use of PEG might reduce corona formation improving circulation time. Continuous effort has been made by attempting various delivery systems for nano particles namely dopamine delivery system, dopamine agonist delivery system, dopamine precursor delivery system, antioxidant delivery system, neurotrophic factor delivery system for increase in the efficacy of the therapy. Modification of the carrier system on functionalization with high specificity ligand is another approach. Development of embryonic stem cells into dopamine producing nerve cells in chicken and mouse models has been conducted albeit with the formation of some extent of unwanted stem cells¹⁹. Biodegradable polymeric nano fibers in combination with nerve cells have been directed towards the brain leading to the gradual decay and disappearance of the polymers evolving new nerve cells with time¹⁹. With these numerous approach work is ongoing to handle this deadly disease. To end with, as it is nicely quoted by Michael J. Fox, "It's about being comfortable functioning on a day-to-day basis".

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